

Publication practices during the COVID-19 pandemic: Biomedical preprints and peer-reviewed literature

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

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1. Data flow chart

Shows the usage of various data platforms in this study.

Datasets used:

BioRxiv API: Preprints on COVID-19 topic from bioRxiv & medRxiv,
<https://connect.biorxiv.org/relate/content/181>

Rxivist: <https://www.rxivist.org/>

Crossref: <https://www.crossref.org/services/metadata-delivery/rest-api/>

Dimensions API: <https://www.dimensions.ai/dimensions-apis/>

Dimensions (Preprints): [Dimensions](#) were searched for COVID-19 related bioRxiv (or medRxiv) preprints¹ and those were searched for resulting_publication_doi, associated with the fact they were published.

Dimensions (Postprints): [Dimensions](#) were searched for COVID-19 related journal articles, whose titles were then matched to bioRxiv (or medRxiv) COVID-19-related preprint titles from [bioRxiv API](#).

CORD-19: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/cord19>

2. Published Collections

Shows how various data were combined to account for all published preprints.

BioRxiv (as of August 20, 2020)

	BioRxiv API	Dimensions (Preprints)	Dimensions (Postprints)	CORD-19
BioRxiv API	171	41	69	56
Dimensions (Preprints)	41	42	14	15
Dimensions (Postprints)	69	14	108	56
CORD-19	56	15	56	71

MedRxiv (as of November 29, 2020)

	medRxiv API	Crossref	Dimensions Preprints	Dimensions Postprints	CORD-19
medRxiv API	763	226	201	282	283
Crossref		226	201	82	105
Dimensions Preprints			206	77	93
Dimensions Postprints				514	223
CORD-19					350

¹ Used recommended query to extract publications related to COVID-19 from <https://api-lab.dimensions.ai/cookbooks/1-getting-started/5-Deep-dive-DSL-language.html>

Scheme 1. Venn diagrams demonstrating the number of published preprints that were discovered *via* a combination of different sources: for medRxiv preprints (left, as of Nov 29, 2020) and for bioRxiv preprints (right, as of Aug 20, 2020).

3. Leading journals

Shows the number and relative fraction of COVID-19 preprints published in selected journals and highlights leading journals in publishing COVID-19 bioRxiv and medRxiv preprints.

Table 1. Leading journals in publishing the COVID-19 preprints. Only journals that published at least 10 preprints, deposited during Jan 1 – Sept 30, 2020 are included. Cell shading illustrates a relative scale: red – large, yellow – middle, and green - small.

<i>Journals</i>	Total Nu. Published Preprints	bioRxiv Published Preprints	medRxiv Published Preprints	Num. COVID Articles	Num. all Articles	Preprints/ Articles COVID(%)	Preprints/ Articles all (%)	Impact factor 2019 ⁱ
<i>PLOS ONE</i>	83	7	76	400	13169	20.8	0.6	2.74
<i>Clin. Infect. Dis.</i>	32		32	431	2094	7.4	1.5	8.313
<i>J. Med. Virol.</i>	27	6	21	445	727	6.1	3.7	2.021
<i>Science</i>	25	16	9	114	1110	21.9	2.3	41.846
<i>Int. J. Infect. Dis.</i>	24	4	20	272	743	8.8	3.2	3.202

<i>Nat. Commun.</i>	23	15	8	66	4740	34.8	0.5	12.121
<i>J. Clin. Virol.</i>	18	6	12	132	252	13.6	7.1	2.777
<i>Front. Med.</i>	18		18	128	549	14.1	3.3	3.9
<i>J. Clin. Microbiol.</i>	16	6	10	48	283	33.3	5.7	5.897
<i>Cell</i>	15	11	4	65	431	23.1	3.5	38.637
<i>Nature</i>	14	14		117	1008	12	1.4	42.779
<i>Ann. Transl. Med.</i>	14		14	57	791	24.6	1.8	3.297
<i>J. Infect.</i>	13		13	68	186	19.1	7	4.842
<i>Sci. Total Environ.</i>	13		13	232	7414	5.6	0.2	6.551
<i>PeerJ</i>	12	8	4	49	1772	24.5	0.7	2.379
<i>Sci. Rep.</i>	12	9	3	58	15169	20.7	0.1	3.998
<i>Viruses</i>	12	7	5	96	1054	12.5	1.1	3.816
<i>Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health</i>	12		12	455	6796	2.6	0.2	2.468
<i>BMC Med.</i>	12		12	33	228	36.4	5.3	6.782
<i>Emerg. Microbes Infect.</i>	11	8	3	16	62	68.8	17.7	5.776
<i>J. Virol.</i>	11	9	2	41	642	26.8	1.7	4.501
<i>J. Clin. Med.</i>	11	2	9	167	2983	6.6	0.4	3.303
<i>Infect. Dis. Modelling</i>	11		11	45	66	24.4	16.7	

4. Publication rates

Shows publication rates for COVID-19 preprints.

Preprint platform	bioRxiv	medRxiv
Deposited during Jan 1 - Sept 30	1964	6418
Published in refereed journals by Sept 30	362	1001
Published in refereed journals by Dec 7	663	1850

ⁱ 2020 Journal Citation Reports® Science Edition (Thomson Reuters, 2020).